

Model and Instrument on Qur'anic Emotional Explosion Using "MGG&TF Qee In nova" Among Adolescents in Malaysia for Sustainable Society

Associate Prof Dr Asma Abdul Rahman (Phd)

Associate Prof Dr (PhD), FPBU, USIM, 71800 Bandar Baru Nilai, Nilai, Negeri Sembilan.

Abstract: Adolescence has to deal with profound physical, emotional and social changes. Many adolescents face external challengers related to peer pressure, drugs, gangs and violence and bring about social problems. The highest number of adolescent offenders was in 2010 with total of 6020, Kedah being the state with the highest number of adolescent offenders by average of 783 in last 7 years. Thus, the primary objectives of this study is to ascertain factors that cause emotional explosion and symptoms to examine the behavioral changes of the emotional explosions, coping strategies adopted by the teachers and counselors in up fronting the emotional explosive cases. Subsequently, the study will develop a model on instrument of Qur'anic Emotional Explosion "(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)" among adolescents in measuring emotional explosion. The research methodology for this research is through in depth interview collect the data. The interviews are the adolescents who had experienced emotional explosions, teachers and counselors who are directly involved in the coping strategies of the cases. 210 participants from five province in Kedah Malaysia will be interviewed by employing in-depth structured and focused group interview. The findings will be integrated with emotional Qur'anic constructs to develop "(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)" Model and Instrument. The "(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)" Instrument will then be validated by collecting data from 30-50 adolescents from the central states schools in Malaysia. The significance of the finding will help the stake holders and related advocate units in developing and planning self-emotional control intervention programmes for adolescents' for their future well being. This research has potentials in molding healthy spiritual and psychic life at study place, work place and in most everyday life situations among adolescents in Malaysia.

I. Problem Statement

Department of Social Welfare, Malaysia reported the number of adolescent and children involve in criminal offence in 2015 are 4,669 cases which is declined 9.4% from 5,153 cases in 2014. The statistics of cases of adolescents involved in criminal by state, 2009 - 2015 presented in Table 1. The highest number of adolescent offenders was in 2010 with total of 6020, and Kedah being the state with the highest number of adolescent offenders by average of 783 in 7 years. Followed by Johor (677) and Selangor (669). The first offence decreased 12.1%. On the other hand, repeated offence recorded an increase of 12.4% from 371 cases in 2014 to 417 cases in 2015. .

Table 1: Cases of Adolescents Involved In Criminal By State, 2009 - 2015 State 2009 2010 2011 2012 2013 2014 2015 Average in 7 years

Kedah	311	460	1,818	1,401	694	421	374	783	
Johor	617	655	502	848	805	726	583	677	
Selangor	562	507	532	698	733	830	823	669	
Pahang	431	368	292	334	334	352	450	366	
Sabah	113	269	256	435	440	379	282	311	
Pulau Pinang		334	332	204	330	277	297	377	307
Perak	264	357	296	297	311	268	237	290	

W.P.	Kuala Lumpur	192	158	257	300	268	301	352	261
Terengganu	242	411	405	193	207	227		119	258
Kelantan	215	229	175	204	322	330		297	253
Negeri Sembilan	181	214	176		316	293	303	210	242
Melaka	196	191	208	312	297	266		180	236
Sarawak	28	216	294	120	412	325		242	234
Perlis	158	92	117	202	170	91		123	136
W.P.	Labuan	18	6	15	30	21	37	20	21
Total	3862	4465	5547	6020		5584	5153		4669
Source:	Laporan Statistik Jabatan Kebajikan Masyarakat						2009	-	2015

Meanwhile, Utusan Malaysia dated 27 February 2015 reported on crime statistics involving adolescent offenders had increased by 24.4% from January to October 2014 compared to the same period of the previous year. The statistics from the Royal Malaysian Police has reported on criminal cases involving children and adolescents had increased from 7,647 cases to 9,509 cases. However, the involvement of the students involved in the crime index dropped by 11%, but the involvement of non-students Increased by 38% (Utusan Malaysia 2015).

Based on the criminal cases of social prevailing reported in the country. Most types of crimes indulged by adolescents and young adults are particularly property crimes of burglary i.e., 1,263 cases and violent crimes including murder, attempted murder and wounding others (Zanaria et al. 2016). Based on Laporan Statistik Jabatan Kebajikan Masyarakat 2009 – 2015, the data have been summarised and presented in Figure 1, which shows that total percentage of adolescents involved in criminal offences in Kedah, Johor, Selangor, Pahang and Perak is more than 50%. (see Attachment)

Royal Malaysian Police (RMP) obtained their own statistics on juvenile cases. RMP's statistics shows that the juvenile (adolescent) cases continue to rise. The report shows a total of 7,816 cases were recorded in 2013 compared to 3,700 cases in 2012. This report involves an increase of 4,116 cases (Zanariah et al. 2016). This situation shows the rate of increase in moral crisis, moral and adolescents in this country more formidable when the statistics show the number of criminal cases involving juvenile offenders increased by 111% in the last year (ibid). The findings indicate that a comprehensive programme should be carried out at the primary level up to tertiary institutions to strengthen the morale of the adolescents in order to reduce the criminal cases involving these young generation. Adolescents should be given guidance on the morale, behavior and solving problems related to adolescent development stage.

Criminal offences done by adolescents not only cause problems to current situation but also to our future. The instigation to such offences close related to emotional explosion especially negative emotion within the inner self of adolescents (Day 2009). Therefore, the focus of this research is to determine the domains and elements related to emotional explosions faced by adolescents such as type and symptoms of emotional explosions, prevalent factors cause to emotional explosions and mechanism to overcome the emotional explosions.

Hence, based on the two sets of data shown in Table 1 and the police report in published in mainstream media, the present study is deemed timely to be explored and investigated. Therefore, the study dwells into the determination of Qur'anic Emotional Explosion "(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)" Instrument using domains and elements found in Qur'an and based on prevalent factors that contributed to emotional explosions. The "(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)" instrument is used to identify emotional explosions stage, in an effort to overcome the emotional explosions faced by adolescents in Malaysia.

II. Research Questions

The research questions to address the research objectives will be by examining the domains and elements of "(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)" Model and "(MGG&&TF

QEE INNOVA)" Instrument. Thus, this study will investigate:

- (a) What are the types of emotional explosions faced by adolescents?
- (b) What could be the symptoms of emotional explosions in identified cases?

- (c) What are the prevalent factors that contributed to emotional explosions?
(d) How coping strategies can overcome the emotional explosions?

Objectives of the Research

This study embarks on the development of “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)” Model and Instrument. Thus the objectives are

- (a) To develop Qur’anic Emotional Explosion Model
(b) To develop Qur’anic Emotional Explosion instrument

III. Literature Reviews

Theoretical

Erik Erikson (1968), a pioneer of the theory of psychosocial development stated that the development of the human personality is the result of interactions between genes and the environment. According to Erikson, human life from birth to death through the first eight stages of development. He believes that in each individual stage of emotional development will face a crisis that will lead to positive and negative behavior. This behavior will lead to psychological adjustment problems. According to Erik Erikson, the way individuals cope with and resolve a crisis that will affect their personality and public opinion against him. How bad solution to a crisis in a stage of development will have a negative impact in the development of his life, though sometimes mistakes made can be fixed on the next steps (Woolfork, 1993). In the first stage up to four (from birth to 12 years), people will learn to love and trust a certain person. He will also try to do something without help from others. New things will be explored, received encouragement and praise will add confidence to do a job but if they desire in the block will make them feel less confident and humble. The fifth stage (12-18 years old) a person enters adolescence in which someone is trying to establish his identity. Practices, values and attitudes they often conflict with adults and sometimes do not want to abide by the regulations set by the school authorities, teachers or parents. At this stage, parents and teachers need to understand the needs of adolescents in order for a character or healthy behavior will be formed. In the sixth stage, a person will enter adulthood. They will create a good relationship with a particular person to achieve intimacy and closeness and eventually married. Conversely, failure to do so will result in the isolation he experienced and felt lonely. In the seventh stage, a person is experiencing a mid-natural maturity. At this stage, a person will strive to contribute and services to the next generation. The eighth and final stage, an adult will make a personal reflection to recall the success or failure they experienced in the early stages. Someone who is successful will feel satisfied and accept him otherwise failure caused him to feel desperate.

Framework

IV. Literature Review

Adolescence “Adolescence” is a dynamically evolving theoretical construct informed through physiologic, psycho social, temporal and cultural lenses. This critical developmental period is conventionally understood as the years between the onset of puberty and the establishment of social independence (Steinberg, 2014). The most commonly used chronology definition of adolescence includes the ages of 10-19.

Emotion

Emotions are defined as inner strong feeling, involving impulse or intuition, physiological and cognitive response, which translates to the external reaction in the form of real behavior (Webster 2014; Izard 2013). This means that the emotional reaction associated with the body's internal activity or physiology, behavior and feelings and real intuition that accompanies it. Accordingly, Standley and Burrows (in Payne and Cooper 2001) suggests that in understanding the nature of emotion, attention should be directed to the components of subjective experiences (subjective experience), verbal description, accompanying physiological response, motivational influences, behavioral expression, and consequences. To understand the experience of emotions and feelings, individuals need to focus attention on the event, thought or stimulus, perception and thought processes, and activate and motivate many aspects of human behavior. These components may harmonies with each other or a conflict may exist between them. Thus, some experts in earlier research see emotions as a component of biology and physiology, while other researchers viewed emotions as psychological components, depending on their orientation (Panksepp 1988, and Lazarus 1991).

Emotional Explosion

The sudden, loud, and violent release of energy that happens when something (such as a bomb) breaks apart in a way that sends parts flying outward: a sudden and very fast increase; a sudden expression of some strong emotions. The ten basic emotions identified by the differential emotions theorist are; excitement (due to interest), joy (enjoyment), surprise (startle), anguish (distress), anger (rage), revulsion (disgust), scorn (contempt), terror (fear), shyness (humiliation or shame), remorse (guilt). The way an individual expresses emotions may be modified by family, social, and cultural influences. However, those theorist interested in the cortical circuitry of the emotional systems of the brain propose that there are four basic emotions; anger, fear, sorrow, and joy (Ortony & Turner 1990; Panksepp 1988). Other affect's states are seen as representing complex interactions between these basic emotions. Panksepp (1988) and Davidson (1992) proposed that the processing of emotional events involve either positive or approach activity or negative avoidant activity.

The adolescent years can be rough: growing up, changing hormones, grappling for more independence with parents, new privileges, and taking on new responsibilities. This can be overwhelming for adolescent. It is completely normal for adolescent to be moody and even angry during these years. While it is normal for adolescent to experience anger, lashing out (making verbal threats, becoming destructive or physical violence) is often a cry for help. There are some situations where anger and emotional outbursts go beyond the scope of "growing pains" and typical adolescent angst. Some adolescent are better equipped emotionally to deal with anger in a healthy way and some need a little more help. Other adolescent experience problematic anger due to an unresolved mental health issue, frustration/anxiety from an uncontrollable life experience, or from crumbling under the added pressure that comes along with growing up. There are a number of issues that can trigger extreme emotional outbursts, anger, and defiance in adolescents namely: (a) low self-esteem (b) bullying from peers (c) unresolved family conflict (d) grief (e) developmental or neurological issue (f) depression (g) anxiety (www.outbacktreatment.com)

Emotions in AL Quran

Majority of us need a helping hand whenever we feel depressed, hopeless, anger and any other emotional explosions and nothing whatsoever is better than the consolation by the Divine consoler, the consoler of all. The greatest consolation lies in the holy book Quran which is established for the whole mankind.

Emotion, an often-neglected, yet significant component of our psychological configuration. Our psychological configuration consists of several components, all of which are interrelated:

1. The spiritual component, as we say the *fitrah* natural tendency instinct, which naturally predisposes us with an inclination towards God and good.
2. The cognitive component, which assumes all types of mental processes we can have.
3. The emotional component, which covers the range of emotions we experience, such as anger, sadness, fear, shame, and guilt.

What is the emotional component?

The experience of emotions is inevitable. Thus we do not exercise our free will in choosing not to have them; rather we practice free will in deciding what to do with them when they arise. There are several key points with regards to emotional intelligence that must be understood. First of all, it's important to realize that if God has created us with emotions, such as anger, sadness, fear, etc., then they must serve a purpose that is ultimately to our benefit. In fact, research has shown that our well-being – how happy you are, how good you feel, etc. – is entirely a function of our emotional make-up (Greenberg 2002). Keep in mind, much like everything else we were given, emotions were created to enhance healthy living but it also carries the potential of being abused. Second of all, the emotional component is incapable of reason; instead, it requires our rational brain to reflect on the valuable emotional information it produces. For example, when you're scared, you try to use that information to rationalize what you're afraid of. It is the collaboration of emotion and reason that results in a whole that is greater than the sum of its parts. Third of all, we use emotions to give meaning to things. People reflect on their emotional feelings to make sense of their experiences. For example, someone may create meaning via the feeling of calmness that they experience when sitting in a religious institution, and they may thus appreciate the experience in a manner that attributes the calmness coming from God. The emotional

component indeed plays a major role in our convictions and worldviews, which is quite often neglected in debates and arguments. This is especially important with regards to *da'wah*/leadership (calling people to Islam); the most common *da'wah* method I see amongst *da'is*/advocates (those who do *da'wah*), I would say it's almost exclusively a rational approach. I personally do not advocate an entirely rational approach to *da'wah* as that would presuppose that humans are entirely rational creatures. Rather, we must appreciate that our emotions play an equally significant (if not more so) role in the decisions we make. Significantly, if you speak to people who accepted Islam, not everyone will agree that they converted because it was an entirely reasonable choice; many, for example, say it was because of the love they felt for Allah, Islam, or indeed, the Muslim community. Although the general Western population places a superior emphasis on "rationality" than anything else, do not neglect the person's feelings in the process. The meaning they will construct following your *da'wah* engagement will almost certainly depend on the emotions they were feeling in the process. Finally, the emotional component consists of two processes: the facility of experiencing emotions and the capacity to regulate it. Indeed, the over and under-regulation of emotions is a significant cause of psychological distress. Let's take the core emotion of fear as an example, and briefly examine how the Prophet regulated it. Fear is a powerful, adaptive emotion that screams "danger!" It quickly generates a tremendous amount of energy (hence, your heart is racing, adrenaline, etc.) so you can immediately seek protection. In the time of the Prophet there was one context that we're sure was fear-invoking for his companions: war. How did the Prophet show us how to regulate our fear in these unquestionably fearful times? Did he under-regulate it by staying at home in hiding, overcome by the need to protect himself? Did he over-regulate it by running towards the enemy on his own, without any consideration for his own being? Of course not, the Prophet was instead the perfect example of emotional regulation. You see, fear is just a warning sign for danger, and this is an incredibly valuable emotional information; instead of attacking the enemy carelessly (ignoring the fear), or staying at home (overcome by fear), he put on body armor and planned his attacks precisely. Hence, fear is a valuable asset from Allah that tells us to be careful. We shouldn't let it overpower us, nor should we ever ignore it.

V. Methodology

This section outlines the research process to accomplish the objectives of this research. This research adopts mixed methods that integrate qualitative and quantitative research designs. Mixed method is most appropriately used when a researcher wants to explore and examine in detail an issue that required different types of data by combining research method from the very beginning, in the middle or at the end of the study (Denzin, 2007; Sekaran 2006). The qualitative design involves observation and interviews in the first phase, whilst the quantitative design involves document analysis and survey in the second phase. According to Creswell (2013) this type of data collection is known as sequential exploratory mixed methods. Hence, this study employs the exploratory sequential mixed method design from the very beginning to provide continuous flow of data in three phases. Figure 2 shows the three phases and flow of the research to achieve the objectives of the study.

Phase 1

A systematic review of the existing literature will be conducted in order to identify the relevant research gaps with respect to emotional explosions. The first phase will involve a phenomenology design in which researchers are trying to understand the essence of the phenomenon by examining the views of adolescents who have experienced emotional explosions cases and the people who had scaffold them. The justification for the design is that phenomenology is interested in the individual experiences of people. It usually involves long, in-depth interviews with subjects, and sometimes researchers will interview the same subject several times to get a full picture of their experience with the phenomenon. By employing this design the researchers hope to gather information

related to the problems under studied. Data collection involves secondary and primary data. The secondary data collection is through systematic analysis and reviews from existing literature on the emotional explosion cases that happened in schools in Malaysia. Meanwhile, the primary data will be based on case studies elicited from in-depth structured interviews and focus group interview. The participants are the identified subjects (students), discipline teachers, counselors, school administrators and peers. The projection on the participants (size and requirements) involved in the study is shown in Table 2. The in-depth interview questions are for identified subjects, whilst structured interview questions are formulated for discipline teachers, counselors and school administrators. Meanwhile, focus group interview will be conducted for peers.

The collected data will be analyzed using NVIVO11. This process is illustrated in Figure 3.

Phase 2

At the second phase, the researchers will review the findings in phase 1, and explore the emotional constructs found in Al- Quran and embedded into the design of the new “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)” instrument. Here, the researchers will also discuss the development of “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)” instrument. Subsequently, survey questionnaire will be designed to investigate the problems under studied. It is expected that a sample of 300 students respondents and 21 counselors/teachers/state education officers will be identified and requested to respond to the questionnaires.

The researchers will review the data collected in phase 1 and integrate emotional quotients constructs found in Al-Quran “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)”. The data is analyzed for its reliability and validity. Subsequently, researchers will proceed with the design of “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)” instrument. This “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)” instrument is to measure the effectiveness of emotional quotients and so develop a fully integrated theoretical framework establishing the procedure and methodology to use. The process of phase 2 is illustrated in Figure 4.

Phase 3

The third phase is validating “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)” Model and “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)” Instrument. The “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)” Model will be disseminated to schools’ counselor and counseling experts. They will validate by attaining level of agreement on the domains and elements in the model. Whilst, “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)” Instrument is validated through data collection from 30-50 adolescents from the central states schools in Malaysia. Data collection from a groups of people is used to obtain information (Polit and Hungler1999) and to “answer questions that have been raised, to solve problems that have been posed or observed, to assess needs and set goals, to determine whether or not specific objectives have been met, to establish baselines against which future comparisons can be made, to analyze trends across time, and generally, to describe what exists, in what amount, and in what context.” (Isaac & Michael 1997). This method is seemly appropriate in assessing the presence of emotional explosion in adolescents.

The research process continues with amendment process for “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)” Instrument (if needed). The significance of the research output is that “(MGG&&TF QEE INNOVA)” Instrument that will assist schools to identify the adolescent’s potential emotional explosion. The process of phase 3 is illustrated in Figure

5. Finally, report writing will then take place.

Participants and Location of study In Phase 1, 70 adolescents from 24 secondary schools and 21 subject (student) / peer group / discipline teacher/ counselor/School administrator from five seven states namely Kedah, Johor, Selangor, Pahang and Perak will be interviewed. The five states are chosen because of the total percentage of criminal cases involve adolescents is more than 50% (refer to Figure 1). These participants include (i) adolescents who experienced emotional explosions (ii) Teachers/counselors who are involved in the coping strategies. Table 2 below depicts the participants in the study.

Table 2: Participants in Qualitative Study (Phase 1)

No Zone States No of schools estimated number of participant to be interviewed.

(Prospective subjects)	Estimated	number	of participant to	be interviewed.
(peer group / discipline teacher/ counselor/ School administrator)				
1. Middle Selangor	6	3	/ school	4/ school
2. South Johor	6	3	/ school	4/ school
3. North Kedah	6	3	/ school	4/ school
4. East Pahang	6	3	/ school	4/ school
5. West Perak	6	3	/ school	4/ school
Total	30		90	120

Data Analysis

Quantitative data from the first phase of the study will be analyzed using NVIVO11. Interviews will be transcribed, coded and managed using NVIVO11. Cross-case analysis using matrix coding and advance search will be conducted to examine the patterns of coping strategies. The stages involves in NVIVO11 include content analysis, word-based analysis, coded-based analysis, cognitive Mapping. Figure 6 below shows the process in closing the original text to final text. Meanwhile, the quantitative data will be analyzed using SPSS 23.

References

- [1.] Ahmad, A. (2006). Qur'anic Concepts of Human Psyche. Qur'anic Concepts of Human Psyche (Islamabad: International Institute of Islamic Thought, 1992), 15-
- [2.] Barrett, Karen Caplovitz, and Joseph J. Campos. "Perspectives on emotional development II: A functionalist approach to emotions." (1987).
- [3.] Buss, A. H., & Plomin, R. (2014). Temperament (PLE: Emotion): Early developing personality traits (Vol. 3). Psychology Press.
- [4.] Cooper C. L., Payne R. (eds) (2001) Personality and stress: Individual differences in the stress process, Chichester, England: Wiley, pp.7–30
- [5.] Davidson, J. M., & Sherins, R. J. (1992). A Long term, Prospective Study of the Physiologic and Behavioral Effects of Hormone Replacement in Untreated Hypo gonadal Men. *Journal of Andrology*, 13 (4), 297-304.
- [6.] Day, A. (2009). Offender emotion and self-regulation: Implications for offender rehabilitation programming. *Psychology, Crime & Law*, 15(2-3), 119-130.
- [7.] Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (2007). *Entering the field of qualitative research*. Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann.
- [8.] Foshee, V. A., Reyes, H. L. M., Ennett, S. T., Suchindran, C., Mathias, J. P., Karriker-Jaffe, K. J., ... & Benefield, T. S. (2011). Risk and protective factors distinguishing profiles of adolescent peer and dating violence perpetration. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 48(4), 344-350.
- [9.] Friese, S. (2012). *ATLAS.ti 7 user manual*. Berlin, Germany: ATLAS.ti Scientific Software Development
- [10.] Garcia, F., & Gracia, E. (2009). Is always authoritative the optimum parenting style? Evidence from Spanish families. *Adolescence*, 44(173), 101.
- [10.] Gartrell, D. (2007). Swearing and Words That Hurt. *YC Young Children*, 72-73.
- [11.] GmbH. Krippendorff, K. (2013). *Content analysis: An introduction to its methodology* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [12.] Greenberg, L. (2002). *Emotion-focused therapy: Coaching clients to work through feelings*. Washington, D.C. American Psychological Association Press.
- [13.] Hacker, P. M. (2009). *The conceptual framework for the investigation of emotions*.
- [14.] In *Emotions and Understanding* (pp. 43-59). Palgrave Macmillan UK.
- [15.] Hardy, S. A., Padilla Walker, L. M., & Carlo, G. (2008). Parenting dimensions and adolescents' internalisation of moral values. *Journal of Moral Education*, 37(2), 205-223.
- [16.] Izard, C. E. (2013). *Human emotions*. Springer Science & Business Media.

- [17.] Jabatan Perangkaan Malaysia (2016). Siaran Akhbar Statistik Kanak-Kanak Malaysia, 15 Desember 2016
- [18.] Kagan, Jerome, et al. (1994) Galen's prophecy: Temperament in human nature.
- [19.] Basic Books [19] Keller, J. (2008). On the development of regulatory focus: The role of parenting styles. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 38(2), 354-364.
- [20.] Martens, B. K., Witt, J. C., Elliott, S. N., & Darveaux, D. X. (1985). Teacher judgments concerning the acceptability of school-based interventions. *Professional psychology: Research and practice*, 16(2), 191.
- [21.] McIntyre, L. J. (1999). *The practical skeptic: Core concepts in sociology*. Mountain View, CA: Mayfield Publishing.
- [22.] Menesini, E., Nocentini, A., & Camodeca, M. (2013). Morality, values, traditional bullying, and cyberbullying in adolescence. *British Journal of Developmental Psychology*, 31(1), 1-14.
- [23.] Merriam, S. B. (2009). *Qualitative research: A guide to design and implementation*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- [24.] Ortony, A., & Turner, T. J. (1990). What's basic about basic emotions?.
- [25.] Psychological review, 97(3), 315. [25] Panksepp, Jaak. "Affective consciousness: Core emotional feelings in animals and humans." *Consciousness and cognition* 14.1 (2005): 30-80. [26]
- [26.] Patton, M. Q. (2002). *Qualitative research & evaluation methods* (3rd ed.). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- [27.] Paxton, S. J., Schutz, H. K., Wertheim, E. H., & Muir, S. L. (1999). Friendship clique and peer influences on body image concerns, dietary restraint, extreme weight-loss behaviors, and binge eating in adolescent girls. *Journal of abnormal psychology*, 108(2), 255.
- [28.] Rodin, J. (2014). Health, control, and aging. *The psychology of control and aging*, 139-165.
- [29.] Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2010). *Research Methods for Business: A Skill Building Approach*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [30.] Sharon Levy. (2017) Behavioral Problems in Adolescents. Harvard Medical School; Children's Hospital, Boston. <http://www.merckmanuals.com/home/children-s-health-issues/problems-in-adolescents/behavioral-problems-in-adolescents>. (seen on 10 March 2017)
- [31.] Sroufe, L. A. (1996). Child and adolescent anxiety disorders and early attachment. *Journal of the American Academy of Child & Adolescent Psychiatry*, 36(5), 637-644.
- [32.] Steinberg L. (2014). Effects of anonymous peer observation on adolescents' preference for immediate rewards. *Developmental science*. Jan 1;17(1):71-8.
- [33.] Utusan Malaysia, 2010
- [34.] Malaysia, Kes juvenil meningkat, perlu perhatian semua pihak 27 February 2015.
- [35.] Webster, M. (2014). *Dictionary and thesaurus*. CD-ROM) Merriam Webster
- [36.] Wolcott, Harry F. 1994. "Transforming Qualitative Data: Description, Analysis, and Interpretation". Thousand Oaks: Sage
- [37.] Yin, Robert K (2009). *Case Study Research. Design and Methods* Sage Publications, Thousand Oaks. https://www.outbacktreatment.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/02/Anger_Management.pdf
- [38.] Zanariah D., et al., 2016. Pemulihan Masalah Sosial Remaja Menurut Kerangka Siasah Syarriyyah: Tinjauan Di Pusat Pemulihan MAIS. Muzakarah Fiqh & International Fiqh Conference 2016. Pp. 153-161